

Photo-initiated Electron Transfer/Hydrogen Abstraction in Quinones†

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I deem it a great honour to be called upon to deliver the Acharya Jnan Chandra Ghosh Memorial Lecture in this Convention of Chemists, held under the joint auspices of CSIR, Institution of Chemists (India) and the Indian Chemical Society. Acharya Ghosh was a pioneer in the field of photo-chemistry and photo-catalysis. The present topic, 'Photo-initiated Electron Transfer/Hydrogen Abstraction in Quinones' as such has relevance to the Acharya's research interests.

In this presentation I would concentrate on the photochemical reactions of the anthraquinones which contain the reactive carbonyl groups, emphasising on hydrogen abstraction and intermolecular electron transfer reactions.

The photochemistry of 9,10-anthraquinones in solution has been studied extensively^{1,2}. The interest stems from their relevance to important photosensitising effects, phototendering of cellulosic materials, photosensitised oxidation of various substrates, their use in the field of solar energy storage as sensitisers as well as electron acceptors³, as photocatalysts in photo-oxidation of chloride to chlorine⁴, and splitting of water⁵. The role of quinones in energy transfer in photosynthesis needs no special mention.

Photo-induced reactions of quinones is either (i) intermolecular, usually involving reaction of the excited quinone molecule with a ground state substrate such as another quinone molecule, solvent, an olefin or a hydrogen/electron donor, or (ii) intramolecular, usually involving reaction of the quinonoid moiety with appropriate part of an attached side chain. The formation of a semi-quinone on photolysis of a quinone in presence of an efficient H-donors like alcohols is apparently a simple reaction,

However, controversies centre around whether the reduction proceeds through a H-atom abstraction⁶ from the carbon or from the hydroxyl group of the donor or it proceeds through the transfer of an electron⁷ as a primary process. The photochemical reaction is more complex in aqueous solution.

In a photochemical reaction since the primary act is the absorption of light, from a photo-chemist's point of view, one would like to know first the absorption bands and locate the band at the longest wavelength, corresponding with lowest energy. For simple quinones, this lies in the near ultraviolet to visible region. It is the $n-\pi^*$ singlet (S_0-S_1) or in some cases $\pi-\pi^*$ transition as in duraquinones. Conjugation of a delocalising group or a strong electron-releasing group with the carbonyl usually causes the intense $\pi-\pi^*$ transition to move to higher wavelengths compared to the $n-\pi^*$ state, resulting in the $\pi-\pi^*$ to be the lowest energy transition. The $n-\pi^*$ excitation involves promotion of a non-bonding p electron from oxygen to an anti-bonding π^* orbital, causing oxygen atom to be slightly electron-deficient relative to the ground state, to give a state which can be represented as a dipolar di-radical from which delocalisation can occur (Scheme 1) while $\pi-\pi^*$ excitation will give an analogous system with dipole in the opposite sense.

Scheme 1

The spectra of anthraquinone in ethanol/ethanol-water show absorption bands at 250, 265-275, 325 and 400 nm which have been assigned to allowed $\pi-\pi^*$, forbidden $\pi-\pi^*$ and forbidden $n-\pi^*$ transitions, respectively⁸. With anthraquinone-2-sulphonate in aqueous/aqueous alcoholic medium, the corresponding bands lie at 254 (ϵ 21 500), 275-280 (ϵ 6 800), 330 (ϵ 2 500) and 385 nm (ϵ 200).

With anthraquinone, the addition of water to ethanol does not alter the band positions. But

† Acharya J C. Ghosh Memorial Lecture (1985) delivered under the auspices of the Indian Chemical Society on December 21, 1986 at Annamalainagar.

addition of sulphuric acid to ethanol (Fig. 1) or increase in sulphuric acid concentration in the aqueous medium shifts all the bands to a considerable extent. Thus the 250 nm band shifts to

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of anthraquinone in (---) ethanol and (—) aqueous sulphuric acid of different compositions (% v/v): (a), (a') 98.0, (b) 88.2, (c) 78.4, (d) 68.6, (e), (e') 58.8, and (f) 49.0% H_2SO_4 , and [AQ] for (a) to (f) = 1×10^{-4} and (a') to (e') = 2.5×10^{-5} M; (g), (h), (i) ethanol, and [AQ] for (g) = 1.3×10^{-5} , (h) = 2.6×10^{-4} and (i) = 4.0×10^{-5} M.

268 nm, the 265–75 nm to 310 nm and 325 nm to 410 nm in concentrated sulphuric acid medium⁹. The $n-\pi^*$ band at 400 nm in ethanol is absent at higher sulphuric acid concentrations, probably due to superimposition of the lower band. As a result of the change in solvent polarity, $n-\pi^*$ and $\pi-\pi^*$ transitions flip-flops energetically. In ethanol or aqueous ethanol, the lowest excited state of anthraquinone has $n-\pi^*$ character, while with increasing H_2SO_4 concentration the $\pi-\pi^*$ state gradually shifts to longer wavelength and the lowest state assumes more $\pi-\pi^*$ character. Similar solvent dependence has been reported in case of acetophenone. Interaction of a quinone molecule with photon of energy greater than or equal to the lowest excited state causes the molecule to jump to the excited singlet state wherefrom it undergoes intersystem crossing to the triplet state. The efficiency of the intersystem crossing in quinones is very high (0.8–1.0)¹⁰. This triplet is the precursor to most of the photochemical reactions. Photolysis of

anthraquinone in ethanol under anaerobic condition produces semiquinone with ethanol oxidised to aldehyde. The rate is pH dependant. At high concentrations of alcohols, e.g. about 4 molar of primary/secondary alcohols in water, the quantum yield is approximately unity¹¹. Similar reactions occur when glycols and sugars are the substrates. Addition of water upto 6:4 ethanol–water does not alter the quantum yield of reduction of anthraquinone; no other products are formed.

With anthraquinone-2-sulphonate, photolysis in 1:1 aqueous ethanol medium produces semiquinone as well as hydroxy-derivatives of quinone, the latter being produced from water⁶. Both the yields of semiquinone and hydroxy-derivative increase with the increase in pH. With anthraquinone, however, semiquinone yield is higher in alkaline pH's and no hydroxy-derivative is observed even at high alkali concentrations⁹.

From the absorption spectra of anthraquinone in different proportions of H_2SO_4 –water after photolysis, the product formed has been identified to be a hydroxy-derivative. Irradiation under anaerobic condition also produces a hydroxy-derivative but no semiquinone even in 6:4 H_2SO_4 –water medium. It is apparent from the spectra that the maximum yield of the hydroxy-derivative is obtained at 4:1 H_2SO_4 –water medium. While in 1:1 ethanol–water medium, the sole product is semiquinone (quantum yield 0.38); no semiquinone is produced photochemically even in 1:2 H_2SO_4 –ethanol medium, the only product being the hydroxy-derivative. The lowest $n-\pi^*$ state (in 1:1 ethanol–water) is responsible for the reduction; when the lowest state has $\pi-\pi^*$ character in 2:2 ethanol– H_2SO_4 no photoreduction takes place, despite of the presence of sufficient H-donor.

Photochemistry of anthraquinone-2-sulphonate in aqueous medium has been studied extensively^{12–17}. Initially, it was thought that the product was 2-hydroxyanthraquinone. But subsequently, it was shown that the product is a mixture of hydroxyanthraquinone-sulphonate¹⁵; the composition depends on the pH of the solution¹⁵.

Clark and Stonehill, on the basis of the observations that (i) the rate of photohydroxylation increases with quinone concentration (indicating participation of ground state quinone), (ii) the yield of hydroxy-derivatives are matched by an equal yield of H_2O_2 , (iii) on anaerobic photolysis, similar hydroxylated products along with semiquinones and quinol are obtained, suggesting that hydroxylation occurs from water and not through oxygen, and (iv) at a fixed [D] and light intensity, the rate of photohydroxylation is independent of pH in the range 2.5–10.5 but rises sharply for pH <10, proposed the D*/S and D*/D schemes (Scheme 2) depending on whether the excited quinone interacts with the solvent or with a ground state quinone.

The yield of ROH is higher in alkaline medium than in acid if $k_4 > k_5$; Φ_{ROH} (anaerobic) = $\frac{1}{2}\Phi_{ROH}$ (aerobic) if $k_4 \geq k_5$; if in acid or neutral $k_5 < k_4$, under anaerobic condition, Φ_{ROH} will be much less than $\frac{1}{2}\Phi_{ROH}$ in aerobic condition, because of $D^+ + D^- \rightarrow 2D$. The detailed mechanism is given in Scheme 4.

In absence of oxygen

In presence of oxygen

Scheme 4

In presence of formate, the reaction proceeds through the steps,

Formation of α - and β -ROH in neutral and acid medium and only β -ROH in alkaline medium is probably due to the reason that in alkaline medium OH^- attacks preferentially at the (+)ve centre while in acid and neutral medium, where the attacking agent is H_2O , it can attack both at the radical carbon or the (+)ve carbon as shown in Scheme 5.

Scheme 5

Applying steady state hypothesis, equations (1-3) are obtained. In oxygenated alkaline solution, we have,

$$\frac{[D]}{\Phi_{ROH}} = \frac{k_1 (k_3 + k_4 [OH^-])}{k_2 k_4 [OH^-]} + \frac{k_5 + k_4 [OH^-]}{k_4 [OH^-]} [D] \quad (1)$$

In deoxygenated alkaline solution the expression is

$$\frac{[D]}{\Phi_{ROH}} = \frac{k_1 k_x (k_3 + k_4 [OH^-])}{k_2 k_4 k_5 [OH^-]} + \frac{k_x (k_3 + k_4 [OH^-])}{k_4 k_5 [OH^-]} [D] \quad (2)$$

In oxygenated neutral solution it is

$$\frac{[D]}{\Phi_{ROH}} = \frac{k_1 (k_3 + k_5)}{k_2 k_5} + \frac{(k_3 + k_5)}{k_5} [D] \quad (3)$$

$[D]/\Phi_{ROH}$ is plotted against $[D]$ at fixed $[OH^-]$ (Fig. 4). The ratio of the intercept/slope gives k_1/k_2 .

Fig. 4. Dependence of photohydroxylation yield on the concentration of D: (a) neutral medium (aerobic), (b) alkaline medium (anaerobic), and (c) alkaline medium (aerobic).

During the present studies we noted another interesting point with respect to the semiquinone/quinolate equilibrium, namely,

Long-range photolysis of aqueous anthraquinone-sulphonate under anaerobic condition (where semiquinone is one of the photo-products) showed no formation of semiquinolate ion ($D^{\cdot -}$) at and below pH 7. Only the protonated species (DH) was obtained, while at pH 10, only semiquinolate ion is found. This observation could not be correlated on the basis of Hulme *et al.*¹⁶ value of pK (3.25) for the equilibrium. However, an earlier reported¹⁷ value of 9.02 which was questioned by Hulme *et al.* apparently explains our observations. As the semiquinone is stable under anaerobic condition, the equilibrium concentrations of its two forms were determined in anaerobic aqueous solution after photolysis (in presence of formate where semiquinone is the only product) at different pH's and the pK value calculated was found to be 8.2.

This prompted us to examine critically the observations of Hulme *et al.* These authors determined the pK values using pulse-radiolysis. The semiquinolate ion $D^{\cdot -}$ has absorption maxima at

500 and 400 nm, while the protonated species DH^+ has maximum absorption around 400 nm and no absorption at 500 nm. Hulme *et al.* measured the optical density at 500 nm, 20 μ s after the pulse-radiolysis of the anthraquinones in presence of formate and obtained the pK value of the semiquinone from the plot of the optical density at 500 nm vs pH, assuming that the radiolysis-yield of semiquinone was constant throughout the pH range (2–11) studied and that the ionisation equilibrium was attained within 20 μ s. A later report by Burchill¹⁸, however, showed that the yields of semiquinolate and hydroxy-derivative of D in the radiolysis of a solution containing D are different in neutral and alkaline medium. Further, the assumption of the attainment of equilibrium in 20 μ s was questionable.

In fact, the o.d. at 500 nm vs pH plot of Hulme *et al.* is strikingly identical with our $\Phi_{\text{semiquinone}}$ vs pH plot (Fig 2 of Ref. 18). This suggests that in pulse radiolysis, the higher yield of semiquinone with the increase in pH is due to the presence of $HCOO^-$ at higher pH's. It is explained by the following steps,

This prompted us to examine the transient kinetics by flash photolysis. Microsecond flash photolysis of anthraquinone-2-sulphonate¹⁹ in presence of formate in anaerobic medium produced a transient with absorption maxima at 500 and 400 nm. The spectrum is identical with that of $D^{\cdot-}$. The kinetics of decay of the transient $D^{\cdot-}$ was monitored at 500 nm.

Fig 5 shows the pulses observed when a $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ solution of D in presence of 0.2 N

Fig. 5. Absorption at 500 nm against time of the transient formed by flash photolysis of $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ anthraquinone-2-sulphonate in presence of 0.1 M formate at various pH values (flash energy, 144 J).

formate were flashed with energy of 144 J. The pulse recorded at pH 11.2 indicated that the species $D^{\cdot-}$ produced immediately after the flash, is stable. But at pH 5.8, $D^{\cdot-}$ initially formed is transient having lifetime in the millisecond region, and at pH 2.1, no species absorbing at 500 nm could be detected because of lower concentration of $D^{\cdot-}$ produced. Fig. 6 shows the pulses recorded after flash photolysis of $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution of D in presence of 0.2 N formate (the flash energy of 300 J and the sensitivity of the photo-multiplier also increased four-fold). With this increased

Fig. 6. Absorption at 500 nm against time of the transient formed by the flash photolysis of $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ anthraquinone-2-sulphonate in presence of 0.2 M formate (flash energy, 295 J).

flash energy, higher detector sensitivity and higher concentration of anthraquinone-2-sulphonate (earlier observations indicated that the quantum yield of semiquinone increased with increasing initial concentration of D in conventional photolysis), transient species absorbing at 500 nm was observed even at pH 2.1. Comparison of the pulse-amplitude with flash energy and detector sensitivity indicated that the yield of $D^{\cdot-}$ at pH's ≤ 2.8 was about eight times less than that at pH's ≥ 5 . Conventional long range photolysis results indicate that the quantum yield of semiquinone at pH's < 2.75 is about one-tenth of that at pH's > 5 and this has been assigned to the higher reactivity of $HCOO^-$ towards the precursor of semiquinone compared to the undissociated $HCOOH$; pK of formate is 3.75. The above results suggest that photoreduction of D always proceeds through the formation of $D^{\cdot-}$ rather than DH^+ irrespective of pH. $D^{\cdot-}$ is stable at pH 11, while at pH's ≤ 6 ,

it quickly equilibrates with $DH\cdot$ which has been detected subsequently. The plot of $\log(O.D._{trans})$ vs time at different pH's are straight lines indicating that the decay of $D\cdot^-$ at $pH < 6$ is a pseudo-first order process as shown in Fig. 7. The plot of k values vs $[H^+]^{1/3}$ is a straight line. The dependence of the rate constants on the cube-root of hydrogen

the same reaction in alcohol ($IP \approx 10.5$ eV for ethanol).

Flash photolysis of anthraquinone in ethanol or aqueous ethanol²¹ produces a transient that absorbs at 490 nm due to semiquinolate ion. Its decay kinetics is identical with that observed in aqueous medium and the primary process is always the electron abstraction independent of pH. The rate constant at various pH's in aqueous alcohol are about fifty times less than that in water. The plot of the rate constants vs $[H^+]^{1/3}$ is linear and has the same slope as in aqueous medium (Fig. 8). In alcohol the effective hydrogen ion concentration

Fig. 7. Plot of $\log(O.D.)_{500\text{ nm}}$ vs time after flashphotolysis of anthraquinone-2-sulphonate in presence of formate at various pH's.

ion concentration may be explained by assuming spherical distribution of H^+ ion about $D\cdot^-$ where the average distance between them (r) is related to the concentration of H^+ ion as

$$r_2/r_1 = [H^+]_1^{1/3}/[H^+]_2^{1/3}.$$

The results thus suggest a bimolecular diffusion-controlled reaction.

Initially it was assumed that the photoreduction of quinones proceeds through hydrogen abstraction specially with alcohols. Subsequent studies have shown that at least with substrates having low ionisation potentials (< 9 eV) such as amines, the initial step is abstraction of an electron, and for those with high ionisation potentials, the primary process is hydrogen abstraction. Our findings in aqueous medium ($IP > 9$ eV) that electron abstraction is the initial step, prompted us to examine

Fig. 8. Plot of the pseudo-first order rate constants of semiquinolate radical ion decay in water and ethanol vs cube-root of hydrogen ion concentration.

is less. That accounts for the lower rate constant. This establishes that even in alcohol where the IP is higher than 10 eV, the initial step is electron abstraction. With phenanthraquinone in alcohol and benzene, the initial step has also been identified to be electron abstraction. The determination of the rate constant *etc.* are in progress. Flashphotolysis of anthraquinone in sulphuric acid and or aqueous sulphuric acid does not produce any such transient further confirming that the initial step in this medium is different.

Conclusion : (i) Photoreaction of anthraquinones are highly dependent on the nature of lowest excited states. Photoreduction occurs from lowest excited $n-\pi^*$ state. Shifting of $\pi-\pi^*$ to longer wavelength, either by introduction of substituents or by choice of solvent causes photoreduction efficiency to be extremely low (if not zero), the predominant reaction then being the photo-substitution. Overlapping of the two states results in a mixture of two products as also observed with some of the benzoquinone derivatives, namely chloranil²². (ii) Photoreduction of anthraquinones always proceeds through abstraction of electron rather than hydrogen atom, irrespective of ionisation potential

of the electron donor as well as pH of the medium. Evidence has been given to show that even with alcohol having I.P. ~ 10 eV, electron abstraction is then initial step followed by equilibration as

instead of hydrogen atom abstraction as

which was suggested earlier⁶.

Acknowledgement

The author records his thanks to his research fellows but for whose sincere devotion the work reported here would not have been possible. Active participation of Dr. Debasis Bhattacharya and Dr. Ansuman Roy, in fabricating the flash-photolysis equipment deserves special mention.

Tribute :

Acharya Ghosh's contribution to the promotion of education, science and technology, development of the Department of Chemistry of the Dacca University, his services to the Institute of Science, Bangalore, the Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, as a founder Director, is well known. To most of the scientists and scientific workers of the younger generation and even some of my generation, Acharya Ghosh was a great planner and administrator. In fitness of things, I would like to refer to some of his research work to remember how great and versatile he was.

His first three papers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, 113, 449, 627, 790) on the theory of electrolytes under the title, 'The Abnormality of Strong Electrolytes, I, II and III', brought him international recognition. Very few of us know that he published this work from Chemistry Department of the University College of Science of the University of Calcutta where he was appointed as Lecturer in 1917. In 1919, he joined Professor F. G. Donnan's laboratory at the University College, London, where Prof. J. N. Mukherjee, his classmate, and Prof. S. S. Bhatnagar were working at that time. In 1921, Acharya Ghosh joined the Dacca University as a Professor and Head of the Department, where he widened the scope of his research. In 1925, he published papers on photobromination of lactic acid, photoreactions with circularly polarised, plane polarised and ordinary light. Prof. V. K. La Mer of Columbia University wrote in one of his papers (*J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 3341), 'Before extending our kinetic studies to include the complications of high valence ions of opposite sign, it seemed advisable to prove that the reaction I (namely $BrCH_2COO^- + S_2O_8^{2-} \rightarrow S_2O_8CH_2COO^- + Br^{\cdot}$)

actually obeys Debye limiting law when the ion of opposite sign is univalent. While these experiments were in progress a paper by Kappana (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 45, and also 1928, 5, 293, for chloroacetate) working under the direction of J. C. Ghosh has appeared in which the same reaction is followed at 30, 40 and 50° for the primary purpose of proving that the temperature coefficient is practically independent of salt concentration as predicted by the theories of Debye and of Ghosh and which make it desirable to record our results without further delay'.

The publication of the Journal of the Indian Chemical Society was started in 1924. Since then, Acharya Ghosh, a great nationalist, published his research papers mostly in the Indian Chemical Society's journal. By this time he had also started working in the field of catalysis. In 1925, he published a paper on 'Catalytic formation of CH_4 from CO and hydrogen'. In 1929, he published on Photo-oxidation of formaldehyde by H_2O_2 in acid medium with tungstic acid sol as photo-catalyst. These were all published in the Journal of the Indian Chemical Society. A believer in the industrial development and industrialisation of the country for its economic progress, he extended his research work on industrial reactions. He started the high pressure industrial gas reaction laboratory in Bangalore and also in I.I.T., Kharagpur. He continued his interest in this area till his death. He co-authored a book entitled, 'Some Catalytic Gas Reactions of Industrial Importance' with S. K. Bhattacharyya and M. V. C. Sastri. Unfortunately, he could not see the book in print, published in 1960 after his death in 1959.

The scientific contributions of Acharya Ghosh and his services to the cause of science, education and technology in the country will be remembered by all and will be a source of inspiration.

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